

**ORGANIZATIONAL AMBIDEXTERITY AND SUSTAINABILITY OF HOSPITALITY
FIRMS IN RIVERS STATE. A STUDY OF MANUFACTURING FIRMS IN PORT
HARCOURT METROPOLIS**

BY

DR. FELIX, OWAJIMOGOBO MACLEAN
owajimogobo.felix@iaue.edu.ng

**DEPARTMENT OF BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION
IGNATIUS AJURU UNIVERSITY OF EDUCATION
RUMUOLUMENI, PORT HARCOURT, RIVERS STATE.**

AND

GABRIEL VIMENE
**DEPARTMENT OF BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION
IGNATIUS AJURU UNIVERSITY OF EDUCATION
RUMUOLUMENI, PORT HARCOURT, RIVERS STATE.**

Abstract

This study examined the relationship between organizational ambidexterity and sustainability of manufacturing firms in Rivers state. The study identified explorative and exploitative ambidexterity as dimensions of ambidexterity while economic and environmental sustainability were adapted as measures of business sustainability. The population of the study is made up of 159 top management staff drawn across 53 manufacturing firms in Rivers state. Data was collected via the structured questionnaire. The collated data was analyzed using the spearman rank order correlation coefficient and the results indicate significant relationship between ambidexterity and business sustainability hence, we recommend thus: Organizations should simultaneously adopt a dual operating system that encourages exploitation and exploration. Organizations should foster an ambidextrous Culture and codify ambidexterity as specification for potential employees. Organizations should adopt exploitative innovations (Energy efficiency improvements, lean manufacturing, waste reduction in supply chains, incremental eco-product redesign) as well adopt explorative innovation (Circular economy business models, Carbonz capture technology, Bio-based materials and Decentralized renewable energy system).

Keywords: Ambidexterity, Firms, Manufacturing, Organizations, sustainability.

INTRODUCTION

The hospitality industry which basically comprise up of hotels, restaurants, resorts, and other service-oriented businesses one of the foremost provider of employment, promotion of tourism,, driver of economic growth, and foreign exchange earnings in Nigeria. Hospitality industry in Rivers has been growing in both scale and complexity, driven by rising domestic and international tourism, business travel, and the expansion of oil-and-gas related activities in the region. However, this growth has also exposed firms to a wide range of risks and pressures: economic instability, infrastructural deficits (such as unreliable power supply and poor road networks), fluctuating demand, rising costs of operations, regulatory challenges, environmental concerns, and increasing expectations from customers and communities for corporate social responsibilities. These challenges therefore has created a significant issues for the hospitality industry and has made sustainability quite challenging.

Corporate sustainability defines an organization ability of adopting business practices that balance economic profitability with social responsibility and environmental stewardship. Arend et al (2007) defined sustainability as the ability to “keep the business going. Boudreau and Ramstad (2005), sees sustainability as “achieving success today without compromising the needs of the future. Lauzikas et al., (2016) sees Organizational sustainability (OS) as the application of sustainable development at the micro and corporate level, through a short-term concern related to the economic and environmental aspects and long-term regarding the social performance of a company.

Sustainability has become more than just a trend but an essential element for organizational survival and competitive advantage. Sustainability in hospitality industry basically covers many

things such as resource efficiency (energy, water, waste), ethical labour practices, community engagement, environmental protection (e.g., managing pollution and using green building standards), and integrating technological innovations to improve operations and reduce costs.

On the other hand the hospitality industry in Rivers state is increasingly becoming quite competitive and dynamic owing to the fact that Rivers state is the economic hub of the Niger Delta region of Nigeria hence the area does harbor a lot of business and leisure travelers whose demand for diverse hospitality services is increasingly high hence calling for the need for organizations in the hospitality industry to be dexterous. Organizational ambidexterity defines the ability of a firm to simultaneously pursue innovation (exploration) and efficiency (exploitation), allowing them to adapt to changing market conditions while optimizing current operations. In a lay man understanding, ambidexterity implies an organization ability of doing too many profitable things at same time and getting result for each. Ambidexterity also defines an organization's ability to exploit its current competencies while searching and exploiting new one. Organizational ambidexterity also defines the ability of the organization to bridge the gap between exploration and exploitation. Chen (2017) defined Organizational ambidexterity as a firm's ability to be simultaneously efficient and innovative. Tush (2015) defined ambidexterity as the ability of a firm to pursue two contradictory objectives simultaneously, namely being both cost-effective and productive, explorative and flexible at the same time, is called ambidexterity.

Statement of the Problem

In the highly competitive and dynamic hospitality industry of Port Harcourt, firms face constant challenges such as changing customer preferences, technological advancements, and economic fluctuations. Despite these challenges, some firms manage to sustain long-term survival and

growth. One critical factor that is identifiable of enhancing business sustainability in a turbulent environment like ours is ambidexterity. With ambidexterity organizations can simultaneously explore new opportunities while exploiting existing capabilities. However, there is limited empirical evidence on how ambidexterity specifically enhances the corporate survival of hospitality firms in Port Harcourt. This gap in knowledge creates uncertainty about the extent to which balancing the extent to which ambidexterity impacts organizational survival. Therefore, it is important to investigate how ambidexterity contributes to the survival and sustained performance of hospitality businesses in this region

This study therefore, intends to descriptively examine: Assess the current challenges of sustainability in hospitality industry in Rivers state, Assess diverse ambidexterity measures opened to hospitality firms, Examine the extent to which ambidexterity can enhance sustainability of hospitality firms in Rivers state and Propose innovative measures in promoting ambidexterity and enhancing sustainability.

Conceptual framework of organizational ambidexterity and business sustainability

Objectives of the Study

The main aim of this study is to examine how ambidexterity influences sustainability of hospitality firms in Rivers state however, the specific objectives of the study are to:

- i. Examine the relationship between explorative ambidexterity and economic sustainability of manufacturing firms in Rivers state
- ii. Examine the relationship between explorative ambidexterity and environmental sustainability of manufacturing firms in Rivers state
- iii. Examine the relationship between exploitative ambidexterity and economic sustainability of manufacturing firms in Rivers state

- iv. Examine the relationship between exploitative ambidexterity and environmental sustainability of manufacturing firms in Rivers state

Research Questions

- i. What is relationship between explorative ambidexterity and economic sustainability of manufacturing firms in Rivers state?
- ii. What is relationship between explorative ambidexterity and environmental sustainability of manufacturing firms in Rivers state
- iii. What is the relationship between exploitative ambidexterity and economic sustainability of hospitality firms in Rivers state?
- iv. What is the relationship between exploitative ambidexterity and environmental sustainability of manufacturing firms in Rivers state?

Research Hypothesis

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between explorative ambidexterity and economic sustainability of manufacturing firms in Rivers state

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between explorative ambidexterity and environmental sustainability of manufacturing firms in Rivers state

Ho3: There is no significant relationship between exploitative ambidexterity and economic sustainability of manufacturing firms in Rivers state

Ho4: There is no significant relationship between exploitative ambidexterity and environmental sustainability of manufacturing firms in Rivers state.

Conceptual Review

Concept of Sustainability

Colbert and Kurucz (2007) defined sustainability as being to “keep the business going”, whilst another frequently used term in this context refers to the “future proofing” of organizations. Boudreau and Ramstad (2015), refer to sustainability as “achieving success today without compromising the needs of the future”. Sustainability entails building a business model that creates value in line with the long term preservation and enhancement of financial, environmental and social capital of the organization.

According to Colbert and Kurucz (2017) sustainability “implies a simultaneous focus on economic, social, and environmental performance”. March (2019) note that organizations are developing sustainability policies, but they highlight that these policies are aimed at developing an underlying “culture of sustainability”, through policies highlighting the importance of the environmental and social as well as financial performance.

Organizational sustainability span beyond meeting the long term goals of an organization but entails meeting present business needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet theirs. So sustainable organizations doesn't just celebrate today successes but also celebrate the preservation of its future. The proxies of organizational sustainability includes financial, economic social and environmental attributes. It is essential for organization to stay ethical and contribute positively to society while remaining profitable and competitive.

Social Sustainability

Today business organizations are increasingly paying special attention to the social aspects of sustainable development due to the pressure from stakeholders ranging from environmental to societal issues (Yawar and Seuring, 2017). Social sustainability basically focuses on both internal and external human resource concerns. Internal human resources may include but not limited to job security, accommodation, health and safety, and capacity building (Ahmadi et al., 2017). Job stability covers the impact on a company's employment possibilities. Human rights, fair working conditions, and gender equality at work are included in recruitment policies. Health and safety techniques for preventing and treating accidents in health and safety are evaluated. Capacity development covers two areas: research and development and employee development.

On the other hand the external perspective of social sustainability basically covers human capital, productive capital, and social capital. While human capital refers to people's work skills or abilities and their ability to bring in money, productive capital refers to specific resources and infrastructure, people's needs to live meaningful lives, and the effect of organizational interventions on social capital on community and institutional relationships.

Economic Sustainability

Economic sustainability is "an organization's impacts on the economic circumstances of its stakeholders and economic systems at the local, national, and global levels". Organizations that achieve competitive advantages through economic and nonviable capacities can survive in the long run, but they cannot contribute to economic systems at the local, national, or global levels. To ensure long-term survival, organizations must sustain their economic stability and sustainability.

Due to the variety of backgrounds potentially addressing sustainability, the impacts produced by organizations are important in the discussion of these topics (Borimde-Souza and Zanoni, 2019). Sustainable development can be seen as an implied social reform complemented by traditional development goals, which do not fully deny pollution and environmental preservation policies (O'Reilly et al, 2018).

Organizational ambidexterity

Giving a layman meaning, ambidexterity simply defines “the ability to be skilful and agile at using both hands”. Organizational Ambidexterity (OA) has attracted so much attention from Scholars in recent time than any other time due to the turbulent and uncertainties that characterized today business environment. No doubt the term ambidexterity is a complex phenomenon, and it signifies different meanings in different functional domains (O'Reilly and Tushman, 2018) and situations, it has been defined, modified and redefined over a period of time.

A review of literature shows that references about OA are found as early as in 1976, wherein Duncan (2017) discussed about the concept and stated that the mechanism for managing ambidexterity include “sequential ambidexterity”. Thereafter, Chen (2017) referred OA as “a firm’s ability to be simultaneously efficient and innovative”. However, research about OA gained weightier attention with the publishing of the “seminal work” work of March (2019). In the last few decades, following the work of March (2019), quite a number of written work have sprang up on OA. However, there seems to be a lack of convergence about the concept. This could be due to the lack of a unified theoretical framework about the concept (Huber, 1991; Yan, Yu & Dong, 2016).

The path breaking work of March (2019) succeeded in identifying “exploration” and “exploitation” as two different activities that lead to OA (Chen 2017). While exploration, according to March (2019) is exploring novel ideas and opportunities that could foster innovation; exploitation is re-using of the existing resources and knowledge that could result in efficiency. There should be dexterity with respect to exploration and exploitation, as according to Yan, et al, (2016), concentration on either of it would result in disaster. Ever since March (2019) identified the concepts of exploration and exploitation, a number of social scientists and management experts have enriched the literature with their splendid works. Exploration and exploitation are both fundamentally activities of business that require and demand differing resources and attention of managers.

Exploitation Dimension

The "exploitation dimension" is one of the two basic dimensions of organizational ambidexterity. It described an organizational function or activity that allows the organization to briefly utilize and distribute all of its existing resources, in particular its own knowledge and to put forward its own existence accordingly (March 2019; O'Reilly and Tushman, 2018). Exploitation activities focus on using its own knowledge (March 2019).

Exploitation is based on the assumption that the organization has complete knowledge of all its own internal competencies and external opportunities. Exploitation-oriented organizations expect to work in an environment where problems are clearly defined and solutions are clear. The focus of these organizations is on the tasks they are currently involved in, their current mode of doing business, achieving their short-term organizational goals and protecting their current position in

the market. Exploitation activities are success-oriented at the highest level and uncertainty oriented at the lowest level (Chen, 2017).

The exploration activities that take place within a certain period of time result in new opportunities and the use of these opportunities leads to an increase in income. This revenue growth and the profit in turn are used again to discover new opportunities. In this way, when both functions are successfully accomplished on time, sustainability of success and growth will be provided in the context of the organization's activities (Lavie et al., 2016, Petro, 2017).

Exploration Dimension

The exploration dimension of organizational ambidexterity defines the organizational ability to search for new ways of doing things, learning through change and experiences. It describes a situation where the organization expands locally and abroad, and invests in the future (March 2019, O'Reilly and Tushman, 2018) for the settlement and sustainability of existing operations to legitimize organizational continuity. Unlike the exploitation, exploration is focused on discovering what has not yet been discovered (March 2019). It is always in search of new jobs or new ways of doing business.

Owing to the innovative nature of exploration, it consumes more resources in the short run, and their returns are uncertain, remote and often delayed (Arend and Chen, 2018). Although exploration creates new possibilities but many well-managed enterprises may succeed in exploitation activities, while they may be weak at exploration activities (Christensen, 2017).

Theoretical Framework

This study is premised on the assumptions of Freeman’s stakeholder theory of 1984. According to Freeman’s organizations have responsibilities to their shareholders and other interest groups. Although there is disagreement over the relative importance of these “stakes”, theorists agree that respect for issues other than economic ones is necessary.

Methodology

This study adopted a cross sectional survey research design. The study population comprises of 159 top management staff drawn among 53 manufacturing firms in Rivers state. Owing to the relatively smallness of our population, we decided to census the entire population. Data was collected via the structured questionnaire while the spearman rank correlation was used in the analysis of the collated data.

Correlation between explorative ambidexterity and organizational sustainability

			Explorative ambidexter ity	Economic sustainability	Environmental sustainability
Spearman's rho	Explorative ambidexterity	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.590**	.494**
		Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
		N	159	159	159
	Economic sustainability	Correlation Coefficient	.590**	1.000	.477**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
		N	159	141	141
	Environmental Sustainability	Correlation Coefficient	.554**	.607**	.488**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000
		N	159	159	159

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The relationship between explorative ambidexterity and economic sustainability:

The result for this hypothetical statement indicates that there is a significant relationship between the variables. The evidence shows that at a rho = .590 and a P < 0.05. explorative ambidexterity significantly impacts on economic sustainability. Consequently, the hypothesis is considered as false and therefore rejected based on the lack of statistical evidence to prove otherwise.

The relationship between explorative ambidexterity and environmental sustainability:

The result for this hypothetical statement indicates that there is a significant relationship between the variables. The evidence shows that at a $\rho = .554$ and a $P < 0.05$, explorative ambidexterity contributes towards environmental sustainability. Consequently, the hypothesis is considered as false and therefore rejected based on the lack of statistical evidence to prove otherwise.

Exploitative ambidexterity and organizational sustainability

			Exploitative ambidexterity	Economic sustainability	Environmental sustainability
Spearman's rho	Exploitative ambidexterity	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.473**	.438**
		Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
		N	159	159	159
	Economic sustainability	Correlation Coefficient	.473**	.000	.477**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
		N	159	159	159
	Environmental sustainability	Correlation Coefficient	.774**	.607**	.488**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000
		N	159	159	159

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The relationship between exploitative ambidexterity and economic sustainability:

The result for this hypothetical statement indicates that there is a significant relationship between the variables. The evidence shows that at a $\rho = .473$ and a $P < 0.05$, exploitative ambidexterity enhances economic sustainability. Consequently, the hypothesis is considered as false and therefore rejected based on the lack of statistical evidence to prove otherwise.

The relationship between exploitative ambidexterity and environmental sustainability:

The result for this hypothetical statement indicates that there is a significant relationship between the variables. The evidence shows that at a $\rho = .438$ and a $P < 0.05$, exploitative ambidexterity

contributes towards environmental sustainability. Consequently, the hypothesis is considered as false and therefore rejected based on the lack of statistical evidence to prove otherwise.

Discussion of Findings

Our findings revealed that there is significant relationship between ambidexterity and sustainability of manufacturing firms in Rivers state. Our study unveil the dimensions of ambidexterity opened to hospitality firms as explorative dimensions and exploitive dimensions. The various proxies of explorative dimensions that is available to hospitality industry include: innovation, experimentation, search for new markets while that of exploitative dimension include efficiency, refinement, modification of existing operations.

The study also revealed exploitative innovation opened to hospitality firms as include energy efficiency improvements, lean manufacturing, waste reduction in supply chains, and incremental eco product redesign while exploratory innovations include Circular economy business models, carbon capture technology, bio-based materials and decentralized renewable energy systems. Becoming an ambidextrous organization is another route that will facilitate continuous improvement and sustainability. Organizations are now striving hard to become very ambidextrous to make them fit to take on the highly dynamic competitive and turbulent market and on the long achieve business sustainability.

Organizations need to focus their attention on the exploitation activities that create value as much as possible in the short run instead of exploration which may not provide results in the long run and in which case, the success rate is low. But if the defects that seem like failure in the first stage are consequently concealed, the long-term new expansions will be available. Therefore, it is important to understand and manage this process well in order to get results from exploration

activities. In this regard, the most important point is the efficient distribution of resources. Transferring more resources to exploration activities may result in higher costs of services and accordingly may reduce the speed of exploitation activities. In other words, too much focus on exploration activities may cause the organization to move away from the economies of scale by substantially losing its effectiveness.

On the other hand, too much focus on exploitation may lead to inertia and it may lead the organization into a constant routine by lowering its awareness of new opportunities. On the contrary, with exploration activities, an organizational environment can be formed in which acquisition of new information is supported by a centralized structure and an innovation-oriented leadership (Adler et al., 2019). In this way, it is not possible to get any result in the short run, but in the long run, the organization contributes positively to its sustainability and performance. According to March (2019), while the logic of exploration is based on innovation, research of new opportunities and change, the logic of exploitation dimension is based on production, efficiency and application. However, what is important for organizations is the effective handling of these two dimensions at the same time.

Conclusion

This study put up a strong argument in favor of ambidexterity as a predictor of business sustainability.

Recommendations

1. Organizations should adopt an operating system that encourages exploration of new business grounds to stay sustainable.

2. Organizations should adopt explorative innovation (Circular economy business models, Carbonz capture technology, Bio-based zmaterials and Decentralized renewable energy system).
3. Organizations should foster an ambidextrous Culture and codify ambidexterity as specification for potential employees.
4. Organizations should adopt exploitative innovations (Energy efficiency improvements, lean manufacturing, waste reduction in supply chains, incremental eco-product redesign).

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